

Unfolding Adaptability of Gradeschool Teachers in the New Face to Face Classroom Management

Mariefie M. De Guzman
Remigilda D. Gallardo, EdD

Abstract. This qualitative study explored the experiences of teachers in Talomo District, Davao City on the new face to face classroom management. Thematic analysis was used to analyze the data collected from eight (8) teachers through semi-structured interviews. The findings revealed three main themes: technology integration, health and safety concerns, and learning loss. The coping mechanisms that teachers used to address these challenges included seeking support from colleagues and administrators, building positive relationships with students, and upskilling and improving instructional skills. The study also found that cross-sector collaboration is essential to effectively address the challenges of the new face to face classroom management and is the main educational management insight drawn from the participants. Overall, this study provides valuable insights into the challenges and coping mechanisms of teachers in the new face to face classroom. The findings of this study can be used to inform the development of policies and practices that support teachers in their work. School heads and policymakers may be more receptive to the current challenges of education, particularly in classroom management, and to provide the appropriate support and solutions to assist teachers.

KEY WORDS

1. workload stress 2. teaching experience 3. lived experiences

Date Received: September 05, 2024 — Date Reviewed: September 10, 2024 — Date Published: October 10, 2024

1. Introduction

The Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic has been a global crisis that affected many areas of society including the educational sector, which has not been immune to its effects. As the coronavirus pandemic spread, the need to rethink and redesign the instructional strategies increased to respond optimally to the rising demand for higher, continuing education. In this unprecedented situation, online education reflected a pedagogical shift from the traditional method to the modern approach of teaching. Thus, adaptable and innovative teacher behavior was considered central to a competitive society that is evolving very fast as the world coursed through the pandemic. In this context, teachers were forced to adapt in a very short time to online teaching. This process of adjustability has meant overcoming barriers, such as separation from students, accessing technological and digital infrastructures, and rapidly developing the digital competences necessary for online teaching, as well as ensuring that pupils had access to online teaching and learning activities. Teachers around the globe amidst personal and professional challenges, reported to have increased levels of mental, social, and techni-

cal stress had to display immense adaptability to the changes required by the pandemic to the education sector. In response, the World Bank (2020) supported teachers by sharing guidelines stressing the importance of: providing feedback to students, maintaining constant communication with caregivers, and reporting to local education units to keep track of learning. Fewer governments took a different approach: Costa Rica developed a digital toolbox with pedagogical resources such as a guide for autonomous work, the state of São Paulo in Brazil organized frequent two-hour conversations between Secretary Rossieli Soares and teachers through the mobile application developed by the state. These conversations and tools allowed governments to have an open line of communication with teachers to better understand their concerns and adjust remote learning programs. With all these support and guidelines, teachers were somehow able to balance educating and providing feedback to students remotely, filling administrative reports, and taking care of their families. In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) recommended to use adaptive learning methods to ensure continuity of education, and protection of learners and teachers from the COVID-19 pandemic. Atty.

Alberto Muyot, Chief Executive Officer of Save the Children Philippines called for the public's support, especially the education sector, to the training of teachers and non-teaching personnel to handle new learning methods for the smooth implementation of DepEd's adaptive systems, and address the emerging needs of learners including low numeracy and literacy skills. The Learning Continuity Plan and COVID-19 Response Plans were also implemented to ensure continued learning. With all these changes in place, teachers across the nation had to display incredible adaptability to catch up to the needs of the learners and the times. In the local scenario particularly in Talomo, Davao City, the changes of the pandemic has caused some challenges to the teachers. Implementations of new changes every now and then required teachers to learn new skills and tools to ensure learning continuity. Through all these, teachers have shown incredible resiliency that allowed them to adapt to changes and therefore, enabled them to be effective in their role despite the hurdles. I discerned there is a need to take a deeper look into the adaptability of teachers throughout the pandemic and to identify what could be done to provide better support in their role in education.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This study provided insight into the adaptability of teachers following the challenges brought about by the pandemic to the educational sector. The strategies in coping along with the challenges faced by the teachers shall be identified by the end of this study. With these, the teachers shall give their insights based on their personal experience.

1.2. Research Questions—

- (1) What are the experiences of gradeschool teachers in adapting with the new face-to-face classroom management?
- (2) What are the coping mechanisms of teachers in adapting with the new face-to-face classroom management?
- (3) What educational management insights can be drawn from the findings of the study?

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following terms are operationally defined to make this study more comprehensive. Adaptability. Adaptability is a teachable skill that gives them

the ability to handle unexpected situations without evident frustration. In addition, teachers can reinforce this skill by educating students on setting achievable goals, scaffolding, and other

classroom activities. Insights. The capacity to gain an accurate and deep intuitive understanding of a person or thing. Stress. A state of mental or emotional strain or tension resulting from

1.4. Significant of the Study—To clearly determine the outcomes of this study and to whom the findings are addressed, the following persons or agencies were the beneficiaries. Department of Education Personnel. The DepEd, particularly the District of Talomo, Davao City, to identify challenges that burden the teachers and to show better support to the adaptability of educators. School Principals and Head teachers. For the school principals and school heads to gain a clear thought on the adaptability of teachers throughout the pandemic and how this

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study is anchored on three lines of research and theory to inform the adaptability construct. The first is evolutionary (educational) psychology that has examined the factors related to mind that assist students to adapt to the learning and achievement demands in their academic lives (Geary, 2008). The second is based on human behavioral ecology that seeks to explain adaptation in situated and behavioral terms (Barrett, Dunbar, Lycett, 2002). The third relates to a motivational framing of adaptability and learning (Bandura, 2001; Covington, 1992; Zimmerman, 1989). Evolutionary psychology seeks to explain evolution in terms of the psychological mechanisms that are needed to survive, with the mind viewed in terms of the domains or modules relevant to meeting the challenges of the environment. From an evolutionary psychology perspective, the mind is comprised of psychological adaptations and predisposed mechanisms for learning that survive because they solve problems that individuals are presented with (Geary, 2008). Of the various perspectives and contributions under

adverse or very demanding circumstances. It can come from any event or thought that makes you feel frustrated, angry, or nervous. Stress is your body's reaction to a challenge or demand.

can be strengthened. Teachers. The findings of this study shall benefit the teachers as the participants of this study unravel their thoughts and personal experiences during the delivery of their respective work despite the challenges the pandemic. Future Researchers. For the future researchers to take into consideration some other aspects of teachers' adaptability in the time of pandemic and to gain other information that may be useful in furthering this study. Other areas pertaining to this study may be conducted in other grade levels and districts.

the evolutionary psychology banner, perhaps the closest to context-relevant learning and achievement is that proposed by evolutionary educational psychology (Geary, 2008). According to Geary, evolutionary educational psychology seeks to explain how evolved biases in learning and motivation influence individuals' capacity and motivation to learn academic subject matter and academic skills. Evolutionary educational psychology proposes two psychological systems that are relevant to adaptation and learning. Primary (folk) psychological systems are what have an evolutionary basis and involve processing information related to self, others, and group dynamics (Geary, 2008). Secondary psychological systems are what are acquired through individuals' interactions with their environment. Secondary systems are typically what underpin performance environments such as school in which culturally-relevant skills and knowledge are taught and learnt (Geary, 2008). One line of evolutionary work that more explicitly accommodates the role of context and social environment is that proposed by human behav-

ioral ecology (HBE). HBE has been described as a more 'functional' approach to human learning (Barrett et al., 2002), arguing for relatively rapid changes in behavior through interaction with environment in the course of adaptation (Barrett et al., 2002). In contrast, evolutionary psychology argues that adaptation occurs slowly and that this poses problems because the world has changed faster than the brain and behavior can adapt to it (Barrett et al., 2002). HBE, then, has been portrayed as more pragmatic and tied to readily observable changes in learning. The third line of work summarized here as relevant to adaptability and learning is that proposed under a motivational framework. According to Zimmerman (1989), young people become increasingly capable of initiating and directing their personal attributes with a view to attaining a particular educational (or other) outcome. Thus, they do not merely participate in the academic process; rather, they actively engage and operate on it. In various ways and to varying degrees they learn that there is a reciprocal dialogue between their personal faculties (cognitive, emotional, and behavioral) and contextual stimuli. Similarly, Bandura (2001) asserts that dynamic and proactive cognitive and behavioral enablement equips individuals with the personal resources required to select and create successful approaches to manage new and changing life challenges. Likewise, Covington (2000) has provided input on the cognitive, behavioral, and affective regulatory processes in which young people engage to help them function through their academic lives. Together, these motivational perspectives suggest that learning and achievement in the academic domain involve proactive (re)assessment and regulation of one's cognitive, affective, and behavioral functions and processing.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research design that was used, the role of the researcher, the research participants, the data collection, the data analysis, the trustworthiness, and the ethical consideration. The three most common qualitative methods are participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method is particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation is appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) is optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when sensitive topics are being explored. Focus groups are effective in eliciting data on the cultural norms of a group and in generating broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as inquiry which asks the questions, "What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people?" Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation that is greater in both depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption is a framework used to collect, analyze and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used for the coming conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. A good research – undertaking with the selection of the topic, problem or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stanage (1987) traces 'paradigm ' back to its Greek (paradigm) and Latin origins (paradigm) meaning pattern, model or example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which

design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm is an action of submitting to a view. This view is supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000) who defend a research paradigms a “basic set of belief that guide action”, dealing with first principles, “ultimates’ or the researcher’s worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains on how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012) reality is a subjective and multiple as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. Reality is constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realist exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the experiences of the teachers related to their resiliency throughout the global pandemic were drawn out. In this study, I relied on voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes, themes that reflected their words and provided evidences of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct for the commonality and discreteness of responses. I made sure that the responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure reliability of result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precludes from making personal bias as the study progress. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible as during the study in order obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln (1985) as cited by Creswell (2013) state that on epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen distance himself or herself from the participants. He suggests that being a researcher he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an “insider.” Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011).I

will identify phenomenology with the use of thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers “hold explicit belief”. The intention of this research is to put together the details about the resilience of the teachers in the District of Talomo, Davao City. I assured to establish a close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that will shed light to the knowledge behind the inquiry particularly on the experiences and coping mechanisms of the teachers during the global pandemic in their respective classes. . Axiology refers to role of values in research. Creswell (2013) avers that the role of values in a study is significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes own interpretation in conjunction with interpretation of participants. I uphold the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and the value-laden nature of information gathered from the study. I therefore preserve the merit of the participant’s answers and carefully interpreted the answers in the light of the participant’s personal interpretation. Rhetorics. This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher may write in a literary, informal style using the personal voice and uses qualitative terms and limited definition. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person in explaining their adaptability during the onslaught of COVID-19 pandemic. As a researcher, I agree with the post modernism philosophy of Afzal-os-sadat Hossieni (2011). I believe that the aims of education are teaching critical thinking, production of knowledge, development of individual and social identity, self-creation. In postmodern education teachers just lead students to discover new things. They provide opportunities to discuss about different subjects and make creative ways. In this situation student learn to listen to other voices. They tolerate others criticism and try to

think in critical way. They learn to respect other cultures and nationalities. Also they emphasize on cooperative learning independent learning, and dialectic, critical and verbal methods. It

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Methodology is different from method. Methodology is creative and responsive approach to understand questions and subject matter while method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study, the adaptability of teachers during a global pandemic was dug deeper, especially for the teachers of Talomo District, Davao City. The researcher’s interest on the adaptability of teachers during a global pandemic became the basis for doing a qualitative research, a means of which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias, (2013) considered helpful in looking for “meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences and phenomena”. By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the teachers in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols and meaning of the experiences will be presented. Phenomenological re-

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—This study used qualitative research employing phenomenology. Interviews were conducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand knowledge of an event, situation or experience. The interview(s) attempts to answer two broad questions (Moustakas, 1994). The data was then read and reread and culled for like phrases and themes that are then grouped to form clusters of meaning (Creswell, 2013). Through this pro-

2.4. *Research Participants*—

is deducted that postmodernism and creativity are embedded in each other and we can find the result of this opinion in postmodern education.

search is based on two premises. The first is that experience is a valid, rich and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs, (2006), that experience is a source of knowledge and shapes one’s behavior. From the definition, human experience is viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge, and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By doing phenomenology which concerns with that “what” and the “how” (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher hoped that the personal experiences and perspectives of the teachers in how they remained resilient during a pandemic, their coping mechanisms and insights were determined and examined.

cess the researcher constructed the universal meaning of the event, situation or experiences and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. In this study phenomenology attempts to extract the most pure, untainted data and in some interpretations of the approach, bracketing is used by the researcher to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or herself from the process. One method of bracketing is memoing (Maxwell, 2013).

The participants in this study were composed of eight (8) informants. The selected informants were the elementary teachers coming from Talomo District, Davao City. All the teacher participants were coming from the elementary who handled classes last school year 2021-2022. The participants must have at least 3 years' experience in teaching. The participants were further selected regardless of their age, sex and marital status. Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most or all perceptions. Obtaining most or all

of the perceptions will lead to the attainment of saturation. Saturation occurs when adding more participants to the study does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (1967) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998) recommends five (5) to 25 and Morse (1994) suggests at least six (6). There are no specific rules when determining an appropriate sample size in qualitative research. Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 1990).

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—Considering the nature of qualitative studies, the interaction between researchers and participants can be ethically challenging for the former, as they are personally involved in different stages of the study. Therefore, formulation of specific ethical guidelines in this respect is essential. The relationship and intimacy that is established between the researchers and participants in qualitative studies can raise a range of different ethical concerns, and qualitative researchers face dilemmas such as respect for privacy, establishment of honest and open interactions, and avoiding misrepresentations. Richards and Schwartz (2002) emphasizes that a fundamental ethical requirement of all research should be scientifically sound. The research must be properly designed and carried out by researchers with adequate levels of expertise and supervision. It should be worth doing in a sense that the result generates tangible benefits. In addition, Sanjari (2014) informed that consent has been recognized as an integral part of ethics in research carried out in different fields. For qualitative researchers, it is of the utmost importance to specify in advance which data will be collected and how they are to be used. He also stated that informed consent is a prerequisite for all research involving identifiable subjects, except

in cases where an ethics committee judges that such consent is not possible and where it is felt that the benefits of the research outweigh the potential harm. A minimum requirement for an interview study should be that written consent be obtained from the participant after they have been informed, verbally and in writing, about the following issues: the purpose and scope of the study, the types of questions which are likely to be asked, the use to which the results will be put, the method of anonymization and the extent to which participants' utterances will be used in reports. Participants should also be given time to both consider their participation and to ask questions of the researcher. In this study, the researcher would follow the ethical considerations as part of the process in a qualitative research. It was the responsibility of the researcher to completely inform the participants about the different aspects of the research in comprehensible language. The needed clarifications include the following issues: nature of the study, the participants' potential role, the identity of the researcher, the objective of the research, and how the results will be published and used. In same manner, this study will be submitted to the ethics committee of the Rizal Memorial College, graduate school for verification and approval.

2.6. *Role of the Researcher*—The role of the researcher in this study was to attempt to access the thoughts and feelings of study participants. It involves asking informants to talk about things that may be very personal to them. Sometimes the experiences being explored are fresh in the participant's mind, whereas on other

2.7. *Data Collection*—According to Creswell (2013), an important step in the process is to find people or places to study and to gain access to and establish rapport with participants so that they will provide good data. A closely interrelated step in the process involves determining a strategy for the purposeful sampling of individuals or sites. Once the inquirer selects the sites or people, decisions need to be made about the most appropriate data collection approaches. To collect this information, the researcher develops protocols or written forms for recording the data such as interview or observational protocols. Also, the researcher needs to anticipate issues of data collection, called "field issues," which may be a problem, such as having inadequate data, needing to prematurely leave the field or site, or contributing to lost information. Finally, a qualitative researcher must decide how he or she will store data so that they can easily be found and protected from damage or loss. In this study, there are seven steps in the process of data collection. First is the site or individual; the participants were the elementary teachers from Talomo District, Davao City. Second is the access and rapport; letter from the Dean of the Graduate School is given to the graduate student for the approval of the division superintendent; letter of permission for the Schools Division Superintendent, the school Principal and the concerned elementary teachers were prepared for easy collection of data. The third is the purposeful sampling strategy; all participants have experienced

occasions reliving past experiences may be difficult. However the data are being collected, a primary responsibility of the researcher is to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for such safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and must be approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins.

rienced the phenomenon being studied. There were eight (8) informants selected in this study. The qualified elementary teachers were considered group of individuals who can best inform the researcher about the research problem. They were also considered as individuals who have experienced the phenomenon and can facilitate the collection of data. The fourth is the forms of data; the process of collecting information involved primarily in the Virtual In-Depth Interview (IDI) with the eight (8) informants. The fifth is the recording procedures; the use of a protocol was used in the observation and interviewing procedures. A predesigned form used to record information collected during an observation or interview. The sixth was the field issues; limited data collection was engaged in this study. The last or the seventh step was the storing of data; Davidson's (1996) suggested the use of database in backing up information collected and noting changes for all types of research studies.

The COVID 19 Health Protocols. The data was collected during the Corona Virus Pandemic (COVID-19) time, therefore, the collection of data was based on the protocols set by the Inter-Agency Task Force (AITF) standards. It is a task force organized by the executive of the Philippine government to respond to affairs concerning emerging infectious diseases in the Philippines which was convened in January 2020. The Collection of data or the Virtual In Depth Interview (IDI) was conducted following the protocols for Social Distancing which

is one of the mandates of AITF to avoid being contaminated and infected by COVID-19. In this study, the virtual IDI was conducted with utmost care so that social distancing is followed and that at least 2 meters between persons was

made. For some participants who missed the face-to-face social distancing efforts, the video-call via messenger, viber, zoom or google meet was used to gather the data or responses from the participants.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study all the data collected were carefully examined and thoughtfully analysed. The researcher first described personal experiences with the phenomenon under study. The researcher began with full description of her own experience of the phenomenon. This is an attempt to set aside the researcher’s personal experiences so that the focus can be directed to the participants. She developed a list of significant statements. She then finds statements about how individual were experiencing the topic, lists these significant statements as having equal worth, and works to develop a list of nonrepetitive, nonoverlapping, statements. The researcher took the significant statements and then grouped them into larger units of information, called “meaning units” or themes. She wrote a description of “what” the participants in the study experienced with the phenomenon. Next, she wrote a description of “how” the experience happened. This was called “structural description,” and the inquirer reflects on the setting and context in which the phenomenon was experienced. Finally, she wrote a composite description of the phenomenon incorporating both the textural and structural descriptions. This passage is the “essence” of the experience and represents the culminating aspect of a phenomenological study. Thematic Content Analysis. A thematic analysis strives to identify patterns of themes in the interview data. One of the advantages of thematic analysis is that it’s a flexible method which can be used both for explorative studies, where the researcher do not have a clear idea of what patterns is being searched for, as well as for more deductive studies, where the researcher know exactly what he

or she is are interested in. No matter which type of study is being done and for what purpose, the most important thing in the analysis is that the researcher respects the data and try to represent the results of the interview as honestly as possible (Montensen, 2020). Document analysis. Document analysis is a form of qualitative research that uses a systematic procedure to analyze documentary evidence and answer specific research questions. Similar to other methods of analysis in qualitative research, document analysis requires repeated review, examination, and interpretation of the data in order to gain meaning and empirical knowledge of the construct being studied. Document analysis can be conducted as a stand-alone study or as a component of a larger qualitative or mixed methods study, where it is often used to triangulate findings gathered from another data source (e.g., interview or focus group transcripts, observation, surveys). When used in triangulation, documents can corroborate or refute, elucidate, or expand on findings across other data sources, which helps to guard against bias (Frey, Bruce B., 2018). Triangulation of Data. Triangulation means using more than one method to collect data on the same topic. This is a way of assuring the validity of research through the use of a variety of methods to collect data on the same topic, which involves different types of samples as well as methods of data collection. However, the purpose of triangulation is not necessarily to cross-validate data but rather to capture different dimensions of the same phenomenon (Kulkarni, Prashant, 2013). Environmental triangulation - The use of Environmental triangulation is limited only to those studies where the findings

can be influenced by certain environmental factors. This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations and other factors such as time, day, season in which the study took place. The idea is to determine which of these factors influence the information received, these factors are then changed to see if the findings are the same. If the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors, then validity can be established (Naeem, Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirements as mentioned was the use of environmental triangulation best suit the environment of the research being conducted.

2.9. *Analytical Framework*—According to Braun and Clark (2006) methods of qualitative data analysis fall in two groups. The first group consists of methods driven by an epistemological or theoretical position, which have limited variability in how they are applied within their frameworks, such as conversation analysis (CA) and interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) and methods which are situated within a broad theoretical framework and can therefore be used in a variety of ways within those frameworks, such as grounded theory (GT), discourse analysis (DA) narrative analysis (NA). The second group includes methods independent of theory and epistemology, which can be applied across a range of different theoretical and epistemological approaches and are therefore very flexible. One such method is thematic analysis, which through the theoretical freedom “provides flexible and useful research tool, which can potentially provide a rich and detailed, yet complex account of data (Braun and Clark, 2006). I observed several steps in conducting thematic analysis. The first stage in extracting qualitative data for analysis from the tape recordings was transcription. This was done to gain greater familiarity with the data and deeper insight. I relied on my own resources to do the transcription with the use of my personal computer and some reliable head-

phones. I use several nights to listen to the interviews to deepen my understanding on the nuances of the language and semantics of the participants. Practice varied considerably in terms of agreeing conventions with transcribers. Some negotiated themselves to lay-out and conventions required, including researchers who wanted the kind of detailed transcriptions appropriate for conversations or narrative analysis. Others were sometimes less directly involved, and accepted the conventions generally used by the one transcribing the information. The next step as data extraction and analysis. I used manual techniques based on note taking and summary while listening to the recordings. My manual technique usually included some process of verbatim recordings of selected spoken words. I selected quotations about central issues, or when what was said seemed important or interesting. I used a number of different techniques as taught to me by my thesis adviser. I marked up transcripts with colored pens or sorted data by cutting and pasting. I used forms of thematic grids and charts, the framework technique as develop by the National Centre for Social Research (Ritchie et al, 2003). This technique was useful tome in the process of coding, sorting and collecting data for interrogation. This technique was very useful in understanding links and relationships between issues. All these efforts and procedure included saving verbatim spoken words from the transcripts, which could be cross referenced to the thematic displays or the maps. To summarize, the thematic analysis method outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006) which consisted of six (6) phases used in analyzing the data. Phase 1. I familiarized myself with the data by reading the whole data set and noting down initial ideas; Phase 2. I generated initial codes, with coded being the most basic segments of the raw data that can identify a feature of the data that appears interesting; Phase 3. I searched for themes by sorting different codes into potential themes and collated all data

Fig. 1. Analytical Framework of the Study

extracts within identified themes; Phase 4. I reviewed the themes and refined them further (at the level of coded data extracts and the entire data set) and produced a thematic map showing relationships between themes and sub themes; Phase 5. I defined and named themes, making sure they give the reader immediate sense of

what the theme is all about. Phase 6. I wrote the report to convince the reader of the merit and validity of the analysis (within and across the themes), used data extracts embedded within an analytic narrative to make arguments in relation to the research question.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—Trustworthiness is all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability and dependability. In qualitative study, trustworthiness is very important because the result and finding of the research study would depend on the process of how it is being conducted by the researcher. Trustworthiness of a research study is important to evaluating its worth. Due to the nature of qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details are required. Trustworthiness makes the

researcher’s study worthy to read, share, and be proud of. Credibility is how confident the qualitative researcher is in the truth of the research study’s findings. The researcher in this study believed that honesty in everything you do is essential to attain worthwhile success. The researcher has no derogatory records or administrative issues which ruin her integrity. Lincoln and Guba (2000) state that credibility refers to the idea of internal consistency, where the main issue is “how we ensure rigor in the research pro-

cess and how we communicate to others that we have done so.” Transferability is how the qualitative researcher demonstrates that the research study’s findings are applicable to other contexts. In this case, “other contexts” can mean similar situations, similar populations, and similar phenomena. The researcher has already studied the effects of using graphic organizer as strategy in teaching reading comprehension. The use of graphic organizer as a strategy in teaching reading comprehension is effective in the domains analysis and creating. With this, the researcher is interested to know the students’ perspective of using this strategy. Gasson (2004) emphasizes transferability as the extent to which the reader is able to provide generalization of the study based on his own context and can able to address that core issue of “how far a researcher may make claims for a general application of the theory.” Confirmability is the degree of neutrality in the research study’s findings. In other words, this means that the findings are based on participants’ responses and not any potential bias or personal motivations of the researcher. This involves making sure that researcher bias does not skew the interpretation of what the research participants said to fit a certain narrative. The information using the audit trail in this situ-

ation is thoughtfully recorded by the researcher which highlights every step of data analysis that was made in order to provide a rationale for the decisions made. This helps establish that the research study’s findings accurately portray participants’ responses. Gasson (2004) states that confirmability is based on the acknowledgement that research is never objective. Dependability is the extent that the study could be repeated by other researchers and that the findings would be consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. A qualitative researcher can use inquiry audit in order to establish dependability which requires an outside person to review and examine the research process and the data analysis in order to ensure that the findings are consistent and could be repeated. In this component, the use of database is very important in backing up information collected and noting changes for all types of research studies. All the data collected must be properly kept for future use as references. Gasson (2004) states that dependability deals with the core issue that “the way in which a study is conducted should be consistent across time, researchers, and analysis techniques.”

3. Results and Discussion

In this chapter, the findings from the interviews with the subjects are discussed. During the interviews, their verbal comments were analyzed and summarized.

3.1. Adaptability of Teachers in the New F2F Classroom Management—The COVID-19 pandemic has dramatically impacted education, and teachers have had to adapt to new teaching models and classroom management strate-

gies. With the return to face-to-face teaching, teachers need to be adaptable in their approach to classroom management. In doing so, teachers have experienced multiple challenges that brought out their adaptability. Some of their lived experiences are as follows.

3.1.1. Technology integration—Technology is still an important part of the new normal face-to-face classroom, and teachers need

to find ways to integrate technology effectively into their teaching to enhance student learning. This can be extra challenging in public schools

since the issue of lack of technology is also prominent. Opportunities for communication and collaboration have also been expanded by technology. Traditionally, classrooms have been relatively isolated, and collaboration has been limited to other students in the same classroom or building. Today, technology enables forms of communication and collaboration undreamt of in the past. However, technology is not available for everyone. Not all teachers have access to the necessary technology and resources, such as reliable internet access, laptops, and software programs, to effectively integrate technology into their teaching. And even if teachers have access to technology, not all students may have access

3.1.2. Health and Safety Concerns—With the recent pandemic, teachers need to ensure that they are taking appropriate measures to keep themselves and their students safe. This may involve implementing new cleaning protocols, enforcing social distancing guidelines, and monitoring student health. Even in the new normal, these protocols still impact the everyday life of a teacher and a student. Participants of the study that the changes and the constant threat in protocols are one of the main challenges they faced in the new normal. UNICEF (2021) noted that a key lesson learned during the pandemic is the important role teachers play in ensuring that learning continues. As schools reopen, a lot depend on teachers to ensure that children will be able to continue their education in a safe and healthy environment; and make up for knowledge and skills that may have

3.1.3. Learning Loss—Learning loss has become an issue in the new normal due to the disruptions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. The pandemic has forced schools to close or transition to online and hybrid learning models, which has created significant disruptions to the educational system. To address this is-

to the necessary technology and resources at home, which can make it difficult for teachers to integrate technology into their teaching and create a level playing field for all students. Go Guardian (2019) reports that while technology is being utilized more and more frequently in K-12 education, many teachers are still struggling with integrating it in their classrooms and questioning if doing so is the right move for them. There are a number of factors teachers consider (cost, ease of use, ongoing support for proper understanding and usage) that impact their decision of how, when, and if they should introduce new technology.

been lost. As a teacher, knowing the facts will not only protect themselves but more importantly, the students. There is also the never-ending fake information and dangerous myths about COVID-19 circulating that are feeding fear and stigma. Mayo Clinic (2022) explained that school policies vary when it comes to face masks. However, whether or not a child is vaccinated, the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) recommends wearing a face mask in indoor public spaces if one is in a community with a high number of new COVID-19 cases and hospitalizations. Wearing the most protective face mask that fits well and is comfortable while indoors can limit the spread of the COVID-19 virus. The CDC recommends that students and staff who have been exposed or think they've been exposed to COVID-19 wear a mask around others for 10 days after their last exposure.

sue, participants of the study agreed that they need to find ways to support students in catching up on missed learning and create effective learning environments that meet the needs of all students. According to UNICEF (2022), learning losses due to school closures in low- and middle-income countries were up by 17Based

Fig. 2. The experiences of teachers in the new F2F classroom management

on a recently released and updated version of the World Bank’s State of Global Learning Poverty (2022), the country’s learning poverty ranks among the highest in the Asian region. With learning poverty at 90.9, the Philippines outranked all its ASEAN neighbors with the exception of Lao PDR (97.7) and Brunei (no assessment included). Outranking does not mean the country fares well. On the contrary, the scoring is such that, the higher the number is, the poorer the performance is. Singapore, a small country with population that is just a fraction of the Philippines’, performed better at 2.8. Indonesia, though more than double the Philippines’ population, likewise scored better at 52.8. The New York Times (2022) published about the widely known “Pandemic Learning

Loss”. Nine-year-olds lost the equivalent of two decades of progress in math and reading, according to an authoritative national test. Fourth and eighth graders also recorded sweeping declines, particularly in math, with eighth-grade scores falling in 49 of 50 states. The data comes from the National Assessment of Educational Progress, a rigorous exam that evaluates thousands of children across the country and is overseen by a research arm of the U.S. Education Department. Notably, the gap is also growing between the country’s highest-achieving students and low-performing students who struggle the most. That gap — driven by declines among lower performers — was most clear for younger students and in reading.

3.2. *The F2F Classroom Management Coping Mechanisms of Teachers*—The challenges of face-to-face classroom management can be daunting, and teachers need to develop

coping mechanisms to deal with them effectively. There are several coping mechanisms and strategies that can be employed to address classroom management issues in the new normal.

3.2.1. Seek Support from Colleagues and Administrators—Collaborating with colleagues and seeking support from administrators can help teachers address challenging situations in the classroom. Support is crucial for teachers to effectively manage their classrooms in the new normal. Mosely (2020) defined collaboration as when a group of people come together and contribute their expertise for the benefit of a shared objective, project, or mission. In other words, collaboration is the process of group work. But it's also a learned skill. How well one collaborates with others will greatly impact the outcome of the group project. He added that one of the best things about working collaboratively with people who bring different skill sets and backgrounds to the table is learning from their experience. Collaborating with team members or even different teams should be thought of as a learning experience. He also highlighted that creating a more cohesive, open workplace benefits everyone because maintaining regular, direct communication with team

3.2.2. Build Positive Relationships with Students—Building positive relationships with students can help create a supportive and respectful classroom environment. It is essential for teachers in the new normal. By establishing trust, promoting social and emotional learning, supporting academic success, and reducing behavior problems, positive relationships can help create a positive and effective learning environment for all students. Participants of the study revealed that one of their priorities is building a strong relationship with their students which allows them to manage their classroom easier and better. According to Collie (2018), teacher-student relationships are an important part of students' interpersonal context at school that impacts their academic development. Positive teacher-student relationships are important for students' academic development. Students in

members, helps one gain valuable insights into the operations of each department and be able to resolve issues quickly. On top of that, it brings everyone a little closer to each other and hones the overall mission of an organization. Yusif (2023) highlighted that teachers need support and professional confidence to be able to manage behavior in the classroom successfully. He added that effective collaboration with colleagues can provide these ingredients for the teacher. It is also necessary for reducing stress, burnout, and depression when a teacher faces problems in managing behavior in his/her classroom. It further motivates teachers to extra mile to find great ideas to help the entire team succeed in managing behavior in the school. With that, the team of teachers can promote effective teaching and learning in their classrooms. Managing a classroom effectively can be a daunting task for one person. This is common for newbie teachers. However, if you get the support of your experienced colleagues, you will learn a lot and that will increase your confidence levels.

many secondary schools have multiple teachers throughout one day and may have a variety of different relationships with each of them. The results of his study showed that when students reported more positive relationships (relative to negative relationships), they tended to have greater school engagement. Notably, this was accompanied by a significant curvilinear relationship such that the enhancing properties of positive teacher-student relationships seemed to outweigh the limiting (or narrowing) properties of negative teacher-student relationships. Noted by Martin (2019), building student-teacher relationships in the online environment are essential for lecturers and students and between students themselves. The improved relationship between students and teachers leads to an effective classroom outcome. This facilitates group activities because building a relationship is central

to effective group work. Building relationships was found to be among the critical factors for students' success and satisfaction. Hwang et al. (2013) contend that learner-instructor interaction and learner-content interaction combined with technology efficacy are valid indicators of students' positive perceptions. Bat-

3.2.3. Upskill and Improving Instructional Skills—Professional development and upskilling are important in classroom management in the new normal for several reasons according to the participants. The new normal has brought many changes in classroom management including the use of technology, new teaching methods and strategies, and other upskilling that can boost the teacher's morale. Johnson (2020) contends formerly 'nice-to-have' skills in digital integration became 'must-haves,' traditional classroom management and instructional design methods no longer applied, and everyone is suddenly required to embrace a high level of comfort with ambiguity as guidelines and expectations shifted on a weekly basis. And as the new normal is being embraced globally, educators are bracing for these abrupt and temporary changes to take root. He added that the need to update and train our educator workforce existed long ahead of the novel coronavirus. In 2019, the World Economic Forum estimated that the effects of automation, shifts to virtual work, and advances in technology would require

3.3. Experiences of Teachers on The Use of Digital Learning Materials Drawn from the Educational Management Insights—Reading proficiency is an integral part of modern education and plays a crucial role in the overall educational success of learners. Therefore, it

3.3.1. Cross Sector Collaboration—

talio (2007) confirms that in online settings, a positive course rating requires effective learner-instructor interaction. Learner relevance, active learning, authentic learning, learner autonomy, and technology competence have also been identified as elements of student satisfaction.

more than half of all employees to be upskilled or reskilled by 2022. Work-from-home and social distancing requirements have simply accelerated these needs. Santos (2022) postulates that in the parlance of teaching and learning in the new normal, the role of teachers has been greatly emphasized to be more that of innovators of change. The changes and challenges prompted by the virtual learning environment shed light on teaching being a multifaceted profession. Teachers are not only expected to be experts in curriculum and pedagogy. They are also expected to meet the social and emotional needs of a diverse learner population, implement ever-evolving pedagogical practices, deal with major structural changes in the new learning environments, and promote digital collaboration. In terms of technology use, teachers have become content creators and designers with the emergence of the online learning space. The researcher recommends that local colleges and state universities create policy on how to conduct virtual education encompassing preparation, implementation, and assessment; and continuously upscale and upskill teachers

is important that any issues related to the reading proficiency of young learners, regardless of what level they are in must be addressed inside the classroom, on an institutional level and even with national efforts conducted by educational leaders.

Fig. 3. The coping mechanisms of teachers on the challenges of the new f2f classroom management

Educational managers should promote a data-driven approach to reading instruction. This includes regularly assessing students’ reading skills using formative and summative assessments, analyzing the data to identify areas of weakness, and using the findings to inform instructional decisions. This data-driven approach allows for timely intervention and targeted instruction to address reading proficiency issues. Abbott (2020) highlighted that in the 21st century, very few schools operate in isolation and collaboration between schools or groups of schools has become essential for their improvement and for the development of the education system as a whole. The use of in-house research both within and across schools increases the validity of both the learning and the collaboration, which, at its most effective, is based on willing participation, trust, and notions of professional partnerships, where all parties are willing to learn from each other, whatever their official or apparent status. Although barriers to this development of cross-school PLCs through in-house research do exist, notably pres-

ures from a competitive environment with a focus on measurable outcomes, a lack of resources including time, the growth of such communities is proving powerful through the use of student voice, staff involvement and leaders’ firm beliefs. Furthermore, a new kind of educational leadership is emerging which depends much less on hierarchical structures and more on openness to new ideas, acceptance that progress is often uneven and rarely simplistic, and a recognition of the importance of personal qualities of all those involved, including the leaders.

Resonance’s founder Steve Schmida defined Cross-sector collaboration as when two or more organizations work together across sectors – industry, nonprofit, and government – to achieve mutually beneficial outcomes. Successful collaboration may lead to the formation of a cross-sector partnership, in which partners formally agree to leverage their resources and funding to work toward shared, measurable goals. According to Barnes (2012) School development refers to the activities in a school that aim at improving educational practices. These activities may

range from alterations in teaching practice, to new forms of collaboration in teams, to changes in the structure and culture of the whole school organization. The process of school development is often started with an emerging vision and the construction of a plan, which are followed by actual changes in school practices. The last decade showed an increase in attention in the educational field to ways of having practice-based research inform this process of school development, for instance, by critically monitoring the whole process of school development or by evaluating specific innovations in practice

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, the implications that were derived from the results and discussions in the previous chapter are presented. Future directions are also forwarded. The purpose of my study was to find out the experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights of elementary teachers on the new face to face classroom management. The participants were coming from Talomo, Davao City.

To achieve the research objectives, this study employed non-experimental qualitative phenomenological approach using an interview guide. In adherence to Cresswell's (2006) guidelines in which open ended questions for interview were applied to get authentic understanding of people's experiences. Furthermore, through this interview approach, I encouraged my participants to fully and openly discuss their own definition or meaning of the phenomenon being explored which their adaptability in the new face to face classroom management.

4.1. Findings—Based on the results of the thematic analysis of the responses from the participants of the study, the following findings and their corresponding themes were revealed: The experience of teachers on the new face to face classroom management: Technology integration, Health and safety concerns and learning loss. The coping mechanisms to address the struggles were to: Seek support from colleagues and administrators, build positive relationship with students, upskill and improve instructional skills. The educational insight gathered was focused mainly on: Cross sector collaboration.

4.2. Implications—The Results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. The experiences of teachers at Talomo District, Davao City on the reading proficiency of grade school learners were revealed in this part of the research. The following themes emerged after consolidating all the responses gathered from the participants of the study. The experiences of the teachers were focused on technology integration. Technology integration is a challenge in the new face to face classroom management because of the lack of familiarity and comfort with technology among both teachers and students. While many students may be familiar with technology in their personal lives, they may not be accustomed to using it for educational purposes. Similarly, teachers who are used to traditional classroom management techniques may struggle to integrate technology effectively and may not have the necessary training and support to do so. This can create a barrier to the effective use of technology in the classroom, which can impact student engagement and learning outcomes. Another theme to the experiences of teachers was health and safety concerns. The pandemic has made it necessary for schools to implement various health and safety measures, such as social distancing, wearing masks, and increased sanitation efforts, to reduce the risk of transmission among stu-

dents and staff. However, implementing and enforcing these measures can be challenging, particularly with younger students who may struggle to follow them consistently. Additionally, the constantly changing nature of the pandemic and evolving guidance from public health authorities can make it difficult for schools to stay up to date and implement effective measures to ensure the health and safety of everyone in the classroom. The third feedback was focused on learning loss. Many students experienced extended periods of remote learning, which can be less effective than face-to-face instruction, particularly for students who lack access to technology or who struggle with self-directed learning. As a result, students may have fallen behind academically, leading to learning loss. Additionally, some students may have experienced emotional and psychological challenges during the pandemic that have affected their ability to learn and engage in the classroom. Addressing learning loss will require schools to develop targeted interventions and support for students, as well as to implement instructional strategies that address any gaps in learning that may have developed during the pandemic. The coping mechanisms of teachers revealed these themes: The first one is seeking support from colleagues and administrators. Teachers who work collaboratively with their colleagues and receive support and feedback from their administrators are more likely to feel supported and encouraged in their work, which can help to reduce stress and burnout. Additionally, collaborating with colleagues and seeking guidance from administrators can help teachers to develop new strategies and techniques for managing the challenges of the classroom, such as integrating technology or addressing learning loss. By working together, teachers and administrators can create a supportive and collaborative learning environment that benefits both students and teachers alike. The second coping mechanism is building positive relationships with students. Teachers who have

positive relationships with their students are more likely to feel a sense of purpose and satisfaction in their work, which can help to mitigate the stress and challenges that come with classroom management. Additionally, when teachers have strong relationships with their students, they are better able to understand their students' needs, interests, and learning styles, which can help them to personalize instruction and create a more engaging and effective learning environment. Building positive relationships with students also helps to create a sense of trust and respect between teachers and students, which can lead to improved behavior and academic outcomes. The last coping mechanism is upskilling and improving instructional skills. With the rapid advancement of technology and the constantly evolving nature of education, it is important for teachers to continuously adapt and develop their skills and knowledge to remain effective and relevant in their roles. By improving their instructional skills, teachers can better engage and support their students, which can lead to improved academic outcomes and a more positive classroom environment. Additionally, upskilling can help teachers to develop new strategies and techniques for managing the challenges of the classroom, such as addressing learning loss, integrating technology, and managing behavior. By improving their instructional skills, teachers can feel more confident and capable in their work, which can help to reduce stress and burnout. The experiences of the teachers on the use of new face to face classroom management generally brought out one insight: cross sector collaboration. The challenges of the new face to face classroom management are multifaceted, and no single sector or organization has all the solutions or resources needed to effectively address them. Cross-sector collaboration brings together diverse perspectives, expertise, and resources from different sectors, such as education, government, community organizations, and businesses, to tackle these challenges

in a coordinated and comprehensive way. For example, community organizations can provide resources for students and families, businesses can offer internships and mentorship opportunities, and government agencies can provide funding and policy support. By working together, these different sectors can create a more holistic and effective approach to education that benefits everyone involved, including students, teachers, and the broader community.

4.3. Future Directions—Based on the findings of the study, it is important that the findings are properly relayed and used by the significant people whom this research was intended for. For the principals or school heads to be more receptive of the current challenges of education, particularly, in classroom management, and to provide the appropriate support and solutions to assist the teachers. The school heads may prioritize collaborating with other sectors to seek financial support for the high cost of educational reform. For the teachers to focus on upskilling and professional development to properly adapt to the demands of the new face to face classroom. Teachers can take advantage of professional development opportunities, online resources, and collaboration with colleagues to build their knowledge and strategic planning for classroom management. For the learners to collaborate and work well with their respective teachers and to make the most out of the efforts conducted to properly manage classrooms. For the future researchers, they may conduct the same study in a different location. Other factors may also be explored to open good avenues for the learner’s enhancement of academic, emotional and social aspect of their studies.

5. References

- Barile, N. (2020). *8 classroom management mistakes teachers make at the beginning of the year*. <https://www.wgu.edu/heyteach/article/8-classroom-management-mistakes-teachers-make-beginning-year1808.html>
- Barrett, L. F. (2004). Feelings or words? understanding the content in self-report ratings of experienced emotion. *Journal of Personality & Social Psychology*, 87, 266–281.
- Beck, J. (2016). *The countries where people are the most emotionally complex*. <https://www.theatlantic.com/health/archive/2016/01/emotional-complexity-study/426672/>
- Becker, C. S. (1992). *Living and relating: An introduction to phenomenology*. American Psychological Association.
- Beckerman, Z. (2011). *The emotional complexities of teaching conflictual historical narratives: The case of integrated palestinian-jewish schools in israel*. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ931365>
- Berius, R. (2019). *What is complex/emotional about emotional complexity?* <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01606/full>
- Bretherton, R. (2021). *Wellbeing guides associated with st katharine’s*. <https://www.rfsk.org.uk/wellbeing?>
- Brooks, J. S., Hughes, R. M., & Brooks, M. C. (2008). Fear and trembling in the american high school: Educational reform and teacher alienation. *Educational Policy*, 22, 45–62. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0895904807311296>
- Carstensen, L. L., Pasupathi, M., Mayr, U., & Nesselroade, J. R. (2000). Emotional experience in everyday life across the adult life span. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 79, 644–655.

- Carter, C. (2020). *Seven ways to cope with uncertainty*. https://greatergood.berkeley.edu/article/item/seven_ways_to_cope_with_uncertainty
- Carter, R. (2007). *Mental health program*. https://www.cartercenter.org/health/mental_health/index.html?s_src=health
- Chen, E. E., & Wojcik, S. P. (2016). A practical guide to big data research in psychology. *Psychological Methods*, 21, 458–474. <https://doi.org/10.1037/met0000111>
- Creswell, J. (2013). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods approach* (2nd). SAGE Publications.
- Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Qualitative inquiry & research design: Choosing among the five approaches*. SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Cubukcu, F. (2013). The significance of teachers' academic emotions. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 70, 649–653.
- Davidson, R. J., & Jones, N. A. (2000). Approach-withdrawal and cerebral asymmetry: Emotional expression and brain physiology. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 58.
- Day, C., & Lee, J. (2011). *New understandings of teacher's work*. <https://www.springer.com/gp/book/9789400705449>
- Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (2000). The discipline and practice of qualitative research. In *Handbook of qualitative research*. Sage.
- Einstein, D. (2015). *Life is full of uncertainty, we've just got to learn to live with it*. <https://theconversation.com/life-is-full-of-uncertainty-weve-%20just-got-to-learn-to-live-with-it-30092>
- Evangelist, S. (2020). *Importance of clear policies and procedures in schools*. <https://www.powerdms.com/policy-learning-center/importance-of-clear-policies-and-procedures-in-schools#a>
- Feldman Barrett, L. (2017). *How emotions are made: The secret life of the brain*. Houghton Mifflin Harcourt.
- Frederickson, B. (2004). *The broaden-and-build theory of positive emotions*. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1693418/>
- Fryer, M. (1998). Some key factors in creativity research and why they are difficult to handle. In *Frontiers of creativity research: Beyond the basics*. Greenwood Publishing Group.
- Gibbons, S. (2021). *Why schools need a mental health policy*. <https://www.mentalhealthfirstaid.org/2021/01/why-schools-need-a-mental-health-policy/>